

Converting Cellulose Nanocrystals into Nanostructured Plasmon-Enhanced Photocatalysts

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ABSTRACT: Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) are promising building blocks for water purification due to the high surface area, tuneability of surface charge and grafting of surface groups depending on the pollutants. In this report we have converted CNCs into photocatalysts, without altering the surface groups, by *in situ* growth of TiO₂ nanorods (NRs) and functionalization with Au nanocrystals (NCs) for enhanced light absorption. The control on the density of the NRs assures that the CNC surface and functionalities are accessible for the pollutant, followed by the photocatalytic degradation on the light absorption layer under solar illumination. This seed-mediated NRs synthesis can be applied to realize a series of CNC-inorganic NRs photocatalysts. The low temperature (90 °C compared to commonly reported growth at 150 °C) of the NR growth provides the opportunity to use nanostructured biopolymers as functional substrates for preparation of photocatalysts using a bio-inspired design.

KEYWORDS: Cellulose Nanocrystals, One-dimensional nanostructures, biologic-inorganic hybrids, plasmonic metal functionalization, water treatment

INTRODUCTION

Hybrid bio-inorganic nanostructures are promising materials for energy and environmental applications while simultaneously enabling environment-friendly degradation pathways toward a circular economy.¹ Nanocellulose in form of cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) or cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) is considered as a prospective functional material owing to the abundance, renewability of its source and its versatile surface chemistry. For example, CNCs with sulphonyl or carboxylic acid functionality show high uptake capacities for cationic dyes as methylene blue, malachite green and basic fuchsin,^{2, 3} whereas amino-functionalized CNCs show a high uptake of anionic dyes.⁴ Thus, water treatment is an emerging application for nanocellulose, but suffers still from limitations related to reusability.

Nanostructured cellulose acts as a universal substrate for growth of different nanocrystals (NCs),⁵ which offers the opportunities toward the design of hybrid materials

including semiconductors. Nanostructures of the latter play the leading role in applications covering adsorption, energy conversion, electronics, gas sensors and catalysis.^{6, 7} Recently, nanocellulose-TiO₂ interfaces have received attention to promote the removal of volatile organic compounds and arsenic in waste water through photocatalytic decomposition. Although TiO₂ can only absorb 4% of the solar light spectrum, it offers several advantages, such as high photocatalytic activity if sufficient light absorption is provided by the external source of illumination, chemical inertness, cost effectiveness, nontoxicity and long term stability against photocorrosion.⁷⁻⁹ Contrariwise, cellulose as an insulating substrate can provide a mechanical support to NCs, minimize the aggregation of NCs, and the available functional groups of cellulose can interact with the pollutant.¹⁰⁻¹⁴ In comparison to TiO₂ NC photocatalysts, one-dimensional nanostructures of TiO₂ offer the possibility to decouple the light absorption from charge carrier transport.

The augmented charge carrier separation efficiency results in reduced electron-hole recombination.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Nanowires or nanorods can also scatter light due to the comparable size with the wavelength of visible light.¹⁸ Therefore, TiO₂ NRs are considered as highly desired structures for photocatalytic applications, and have been demonstrated to exhibit high photocatalytic activity on mineralization of many organic and microbial contaminants under UV irradiation.^{19, 20} For example, Lv et al. has proved that TiO₂ nanowires have better photodegradation activity on methylene blue than TiO₂ nanotubes under UV irradiation.²¹

However, the wide electronic band gap of TiO₂ (3.0–3.2 eV) still confines the application of potential cellulose-TiO₂ hybrids to the UV region.^{22, 23} Surface decoration with plasmonic nanostructures is a potential way to extend the absorption towards the visible region.²⁴⁻²⁶ Modification of the semiconductor surface with plasmonic Au and Ag NCs has shown a strong enhancement on photocatalytic activity in the visible region via the local surface plasmon resonance (LSPR).²⁷⁻²⁹ The LSPR arises from collective oscillation of free electrons in the conduction band (CB) as a response to the electromagnetic field of incident light.³⁰ Meanwhile, the highly energetic electrons generated from the plasmon decay, described frequently as 'hot electrons', escape to the CB of semiconductors over the Schottky barrier and participate in the photocatalytic process.³¹⁻³⁴ As a result, the deposition of Au NCs on TiO₂ has become a promising interfacial structure for dye degradation in the longer wavelength region. Although the synthesis of cellulose-TiO₂ hybrids by impregnation of a Ti-precursor on cellulose and subsequent annealing is today established, precise control on the nanoscopic level has not been achieved so far. For the fabrication of hierarchical semiconductor nanostructures with well-defined semiconductor interfaces on cellulose, allowing to take advantage of suitable band alignment, it is a critical requirement to control the nucleation.

In this work, we demonstrate that CNCs can be used as a functional substrate to grow TiO₂ NRs and thus yield nanostructured hybrid biologic-inorganic NR photocatalysts (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of seed mediated TiO₂ NR synthesis, Au NCs deposition and suggested photocatalytic process for dye degradation.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150).

CNCs were synthesized from microcrystalline cellulose using H₂SO₄ hydrolysis according to Bondesson³⁵ et al (See image S1a) and hence obtained CNC suspensions were freeze dried. 0.01 g of CNCs were ultrasonically dispersed in absolute ethanol (10 ml) in a capped bottle, and then stirred for 1 h to form a homogeneous suspension. Titanium Butoxide (0.01 mL) was injected into the suspension, which was further stirred for 1 h and then the solution was allowed to age at 60 °C for 3 hrs. The suspension was filtered, dried and annealed at 100 °C to produce TiO₂ seeds on the CNCs. For synthesizing CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90), the seed deposited CNCs were dispersed in 10 mL of DI water and mixed with equal amount of conc. HCl and stirred for 1 hr to get an homogeneous solution. Then 1 mL TiCl₄ solution was added and heated to 90 °C for 5 hrs with stirring. The obtained CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) were filtered and washed with water, followed by ethanol to remove unreacted species and dried at vacuum at 60 °C for 12 hrs. It has to be noted that there was no autoclave used in this method. The synthesis was carried out at ambient temperature and pressure to make it suitable for specific low temperature substrates, such as CNCs or other polymer substrates.

For the preparation of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), seed coated CNCs were ultrasonically dispersed in DI water (25 mL), mixed with conc. HCl (25 mL) and 1.0 mL of Ti(OBu)₄, and the resulting solution was placed in a 60 mL Teflon-lined autoclave. After stirring for 5 min, the autoclave was sealed and heated to 150 °C for 4 h and then allowed to cool to RT. The as-obtained product was washed successively with DI water and ethanol to remove any residual ionic species, and finally dried in vacuum at 60 °C for 12 h. Similar process was followed for CNCs with carboxyl and phosphoryl groups as well (see Figure S1 for corresponding images).

Preparation of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90)/Au NCs and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs.

The Au NCs were synthesized by colloidal method.³⁶ In detail, 20 ml of 1-octadecene (90%, Aldrich) was loaded in a three-neck flask and degassed with nitrogen at 130 °C for 30 min. After cooling down to room temperature, 1.316 ml (4 mmol) oleylamine (90%, Aldrich), 1 g (4 mmol) 1,2-hexadecanediol (90%, Aldrich) and 299.2 mg (0.8 mmol) anhydrous gold(III) acetate (99%, Alfa Aesar) were added into the flask. Then the temperature was increased to 200 °C under nitrogen flow for 2 h, after which the solution was cooled down again to room temperature. 35 ml ethanol (99.95%, Geyer Chemsolute GmbH) was added into the solution to precipitate the NCs and centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 20 min. The Au NCs were redispersed in hexane after being washed once with ethanol. The composites CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90)/Au NCs and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs were fabricated by adding the respective CNC/TiO₂-NRs powder to a hexane dispersion of Au NCs. The mixture was sonicated for 5 min and dried under ambient atmosphere for 24 h.

Characterization. Thermal gravity analysis (TGA, Perkin Elmer TGA 7) measurement was used for the thermal properties of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), the heating rate was 10 °C /min in air. For the Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) study on CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), the JEOL 7000F electron

microscope with an accelerating voltage of 15 kV was used. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis is carried out using Panalytical X'Pert alpha1 with Cu-K α 1 line. Raman analysis is carried out using Horiba Labram HR 800 with 532 nm laser in the spectral range of 100-1000 nm. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images including high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images, selected area electron diffraction (SAED) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) as well as High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) micrograph were obtained by JEOL-2100F field emission transmission electron microscopy. The optical properties of different samples were studied using UV-vis spectrophotometer (Agilent Cary 5000) in the spectral range of 250–800 nm.

Photocatalytic experiments. The degradation rate of Rhodamine B (RhB, pure, Acros) was employed to evaluate the photocatalytic performance of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90)/Au NCs and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs and the hydrogen peroxide (35 wt.%, ACROS) was used as electrons scavengers. The solution was illuminated with 100 mW cm⁻² AM 1.5G light (1 sun) generated by a solar light simulator (class-AAA 94023A, Newport) with an ozone-free 450 W xenon short-arc lamp. For each experiment, 200 mg of sample was placed in 50 ml of aqueous solution of RhB (8 ppm). For every 20 min, an appropriate amount of solution was taken out and filtered to remove the solid catalyst particles, and the degradation rate of RhB in the solution was determined as a function of irradiation time using the intensity of the main absorbance band at the wavelength of 555 nm by UV-vis spectroscopy (WPA S800 +, Biochrom).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seed-mediated synthesis at low temperature is known as NR synthesis methodology for binary metal oxides, such as ZnO and CuO.¹⁴ However, it is limited to the substrates which need to be annealed at 500 °C due to the lack of necessary and sufficient crystallinity/orientation in promoting one directional crystal growth. This is the main reason why previous reports were all conducted on highly thermally stable substrates such as FTO, carbon fibers etc.^{37, 38} In the present study, we have synthesized TiO₂ seeds using sol-gel method with a slow hydrolysis of Ti(OBu)₄ in absolute ethanol and increased the crystallinity by aging at 60 °C (see supporting information for the details of the process). During the hydrolysis, TiO₂ nanosheets are formed and subsequent aging results in their rolling-up to particle structures with a mean particle size of 30 nm. As shown in Figure 1A, the SAED patterns indicate that the polycrystalline particles crystallize mainly with the anatase-type structure.

In the following step, we have exposed the seed coated CNCs in two different growth media, resulting in two different growth mechanisms. Low temperature growth has been carried out at 90 °C using equivalent amount of conc. HCl and water with 1 ml TiCl₄ as precursor. The formed TiO₂ NRs have a maximum 1 μ m length and 50 nm diameter (Figure 1B). It should be noted that the latter is synthesized using autoclave method at the higher temperature, so it may adversely affect the surface functional groups on CNCs compared to CNC/TiO₂-NRs (90). The thickness of the walls

of the TiO₂ NRs synthesized at low temperature was found to be 4-5 nm (Figure 1B). The high temperature synthesis was carried out hydrothermally in an autoclave using Ti(OBu)₄ as precursor as reported in the previous reports.³⁷ Thus, synthesized NRs had 100 nm diameter and 1 μ m length (Figure 1C). This is in contrast to previous reports showed equivalent amount conc. HCl and water with Ti precursor producing rutile phase NRs.³⁹

Figure 1. TEM images of (A) TiO₂ nanosheets, nanoseeds and corresponding SAED pattern of TiO₂ nanoseeds, (B)TEM images of TiO₂-NRs(90) and HRTEM image of the walls of TiO₂ NRs (90), SEM images of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and the flow birefringence of the hybrid(inset)(C) TEM image of TiO₂-NRs(150) and HRTEM image of boundary of TiO₂ NRs (150), SEM images of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) and the inset image showing the birefringence of the hybrids.

One of the main parameters we have chosen for the optimization of the NR synthesis was well defined vertically grown (radially arranged on CNCs) NRs which is confirmed by SEM images (Figure 1B, C). Birefringence, a characteristic property of anisotropic CNCs due to flow induced alignment, was retained in the hybrids (inset Fig 1B, C) indicating that nano-properties of CNCs are maintained. It was noted that the growth without pre-seed deposition does not form NRs but rather formed a thick coating of TiO₂. The TGA analysis of the CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) was carried out in air. As shown in Figure S2, the CNC/TiO₂-NRs has about 86% loading of TiO₂ on the CNC surface.

Figure 2. (A) XRD patterns of CNC, CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) and (B) Raman patterns of CNC, CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)

To understand and further confirm the phase of the synthesized NRs, powder XRD analysis has been carried out. The XRD patterns of synthesized CNC, CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) are shown in Figure 2A. The CNC shows its characteristic reflection peaks of cellulose I at 15.4° and 22.6°. In the patterns of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), the characteristic peaks has merged into one broad peak at 18.2°. CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) exhibits predominant peaks at 25.5°, 36.3° and 48.1°, which correspond to the anatase phase (101), (004) and (200) planes (JCPDS 21-1272). Besides, the peaks at 27.7°, 41.4°, 54.5° and 63.0° correspond to rutile phase planes. For the CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) sample, the reflection peaks at 27.6°, 36.2°, 41.4°, 44.2°, 54.6°, 56.8° and 63.0° represent the corresponding rutile planes (110), (101), (111), (210), (211) (220) and (002) as per JCPDS 21-1276. Thus, CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) sample has a higher degree of the anatase and rutile phases. This also suggests that the CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) sample has a higher degree of crystallinity dominated by the rutile phase.

In addition, the different phases can be further identified in the Raman patterns (Figure 2B). The existence of

metastable anatase can be confirmed with very sharp and intense peak at 147 cm⁻¹ (instead of 144 cm⁻¹ and the shoulder at 192 (197) and 624 (635) for CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90). However, CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) shows very clear defined peaks at 238 (242), 438 (446) and 604 (610) of the rutile phase.

To overcome the low absorption of TiO₂ in the visible light region, i.e. extend the potential photocatalytic performance to the visible region, monodisperse spherical Au NCs were decorated on the CNC/TiO₂-NRs. The mean particle size of the Au NCs before deposition was 8 nm (Figure S3). The surface characteristic of the plasmon-enhanced photocatalyst CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs was studied by electron microscopy. Figure 3 shows TEM images of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs and corresponding elemental maps based on EDS. The HAADF STEM micrograph in Figure 3B clearly reveals the deposition of Au NCs with diameter in the range of 8–40 nm. The increased particle size of the Au NCs on the NRs is due to agglomeration of the monodisperse Au NCs. The spatial element distribution was confirmed by EDS mapping (Figure 3C). The white spots corresponding to Au NCs are distributed along the TiO₂ NRs, which demonstrates the relatively good uniform distribution of Au NCs over the surface of TiO₂ NRs.

The optical properties of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), without and with Au NCs, were characterized by UV-VIS spectroscopy (Figure S4). The typical broad absorption peaks are attributed to LSPR in the range 500–600 nm. The broadening LSPR peaks originated not only from the broad size distributions of Au NCs (8–40 nm), which has been identified by TEM (*vide supra*), but also from the intercoupling of Au NCs. An enhanced light absorption property in visible region can significantly increase the photogenerated electron-hole pairs and is beneficial for photocatalytic reactions. We evaluated the solar photocatalytic performance for each sample on RhB degradation. Illumination was carried out under simulated sunlight by using an AM 1.5G filter.

It is known that H₂O₂ can improve the photocatalytic performance of TiO₂ on dye degradation by inhibiting electron-hole pairs' recombination. H₂O₂ not only works as a scavenger of electrons in CB but also helps with the formation of superoxide radical ions like hydroxyl radicals, which are known as a powerful oxidizing agents for organic degradation. Therefore, the degradation rate of H₂O₂ on RhB under simulated sunlight was set as a baseline as shown in Figure 4. Photocatalytic activities of different samples have been studied in the same condition with H₂O₂ with an initial concentration of RhB being equal 8 ppm. The results of the photocatalytic decomposition of RhB indicate that the deposition of Au NCs can ameliorate the photocatalytic performance of both biologic-inorganic hybrid photocatalysts CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150).

Figure 3. TEM images of Au NCs deposited TiO₂-NRs(150): (A) morphology of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs; (B) HAADF STEM micrograph of TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs and corresponding (C) EDS mapping of Au, Ti and O.

To eliminate the interference of dye photosensitization effect on the high dye degradation performance under solar illumination, the decomposition of RhB was compared with CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150). Since the Au-functionalized photocatalysts show increased removal efficiency, the LSPR effect plays a key role in the improvement of dye degradation performance on the CNC/TiO₂ photocatalysts. The energy transfer from plasmonic metal to semiconductor in the form of energetic electrons activates O–O bonds and forms reactive oxygen species, allowing the degradation of RhB in our case.⁵¹ The possible mechanisms for the nanostructured plasmon-enhanced CNC/TiO₂-NRs photocatalysts are proposed in Scheme 1. The LSPR effect of Au NCs produces a large number of photogenerated electrons and holes which can participate in the photodegradation process, leading to an improvement of photocatalytic activity.

Figure 4. Photodegradation of RhB (8 ppm in 50 ml of aqueous solution) under simulated sunlight on different photocatalysts (200 mg, powder) supported by H₂O₂. The solution was illuminated with 100 mW cm⁻² AM 1.5G light (1 sun).

CONCLUSION

In summary, the growth of TiO₂ NRs on CNCs retaining the surface functional groups using seed mediated synthesis introduces a new concept of using functionalized substrates to grow inorganic nanostructured photocatalysts. Further modification by using plasmonic NCs augmented the light absorption and thus photocatalytic activity of the CNCs/TiO₂-NRs. Seed mediated synthesis for TiO₂ NRs at 90 °C was demonstrated by using a novel process. The presented method has thus the potential for the production of self-cleaning textiles or wearable dye sensitized solar cells, which were limited up to now to carbon based or high temperature stable substrates. The hierarchical CNC/TiO₂-NRs structure can serve as template for consecutive functionalization with a second semiconductor, exhibiting a more narrow electronic bandgap, in order to enhance light absorption and ameliorate charge carrier separation by band alignment.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website. Information provided include Figure S1. (a) AFM images of typical CNCs produced by sulphuric acid hydrolysis and (b-d) CNC/TiO₂-NRs hybrids based on sulphonyl, carboxyl and phosphoryl functionalized CNC nanocrystals; Figure S2. TGA curves of the CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90) and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) (ramp 10 °C/min, 35–850 °C, in air); Figure S3 TEM image of Au NCs before decoration; Figure S4 UV-Vis light absorption spectra of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90), CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90)/Au NCs and CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs; Degradation mechanism while using solar simulator

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

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Author Contributions

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SSN was responsible for the synthesis and characterization of CNC-TiO₂-NRs. JC was responsible for Au NCs decoration and photocatalytic studies. AS and AM contributed to all discussion and manuscript preparation. The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Converting Cellulose Nanocrystals into Nanostructured Plasmon-Enhanced Photocatalysts

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Figure S1. (a) AFM images of typical CNCs produced by sulphuric acid hydrolysis and (b-d) CNC/TiO₂-NRs hybrids based on sulphonyl, carboxyl and phosphoryl functionalized CNC nanocrystals.

Figure S2. TGA curves of the CNC/TiO₂-NRs (90), CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150) (ramp 10 °C/min, 35–850 °C, in air)

Figure S3. TEM image of Au NCs before decoration

Figure S4. UV-Vis light absorption spectra of CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90), CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150), CNC/TiO₂-NRs(90)/Au NCs, CNC/TiO₂-NRs(150)/Au NCs

Degradation mechanism

During the solar simulator illumination, LSPR-induced hot electrons in Au NCs on the surface of TiO₂ NRs with energies higher than the Schottky barrier energy can be injected into the conductive band (CB) of TiO₂.¹ This process can significantly promote the separation of electron-hole pairs. The injected electrons in CB are trapped by absorbed O₂ molecules and then participated in the photoreduction reaction to get $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$. However, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ is quite unstable in aqueous solution, so that it would readily decompose into hydroxyl radicals.^{2,3}

After the transfer of hot electrons, the holes on Au NCs are supposed to participate in photo-oxidation reaction with superoxide anion radicals $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, yielding singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$).⁴

The photolysis of hydrogen peroxide in aqueous to hydroxyl radicals happened simultaneously, following the reaction:

Finally, the reactive oxygen species including $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ and $^1\text{O}_2$ can easily degrade RhB into CO₂ and H₂O.^{5,6}

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